

Improving the Monitoring and Management of Constipation in Patients Taking Antipsychotics

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Trigger & Problem Statement

- Increase in hospitalizations related to severe constipation and fecal impaction during the fourth quarter 2021.
- One mortality from small bowel obstruction during the second quarter 2022

The problem this project addressed was the lack of valid screening tools for the early detection and management of constipation among patients using antipsychotics in a psychiatric inpatient setting.

Purpose & Aim

- Improve the early detection and management of constipation in adult patients taking antipsychotic medications by introducing a constipation care bundle that incorporates:
 - Bristol Stool Form Scale (BSFS)
 - Educational Material for Staff and Patients
 - EHR alert system

The project aims to decrease the burden of constipation and incidence, prevent serious complications and hospitalizations, and thereby improve patient care outcomes

Review of Literature

- Electronic Database searched included: PubMed, CINAHL, Scopus, and Google Scholar

Four Themes Identified:

- Antipsychotic-induced constipation (AIC) exists
- Antipsychotics with a high propensity to induce constipation: Clozaril and Olanzapine
- Limit and gaps in approaches to screening and treatment
- BSFS tool for early detection and management of AIC

References

Background

- Constipation is common in patients with psychiatric disorders.
- In patients with schizophrenia: a 36.3% prevalence
- In patients with depression: a 57.7% prevalence
- Fatal consequences: 12% to 22% reported serious adverse events related to constipation
- Constipation can be overlooked & underreported by clinical staff due to patients:
 - Challenges in self-care
 - Challenges in health awareness
 - Higher pain threshold

Framework

Clinical Implications

- BSFS is an easy and applicable tool in a clinical psychiatric inpatient setting
- EM and the EHR alert system can increase the clinical staff's knowledge and awareness of the constipation side effects of antipsychotics and assist the MD/NP in clinical decision-making.

Results

- Two-tailed paired samples t-test showed the mean pretest scores significantly lower than the mean of posttest scores ($p < .001$)
- Control c-Chart showed increased identification of constipation post-implementation starting week 25 of post-implementation based on MOM PRN given.

Discussions

- Outcomes indicated that implementing care bundle is a practical approach to the early detection and management of constipation in patients taking antipsychotics, thereby preventing adverse consequences
- Increase in the number of patients identified with constipation post-implementation
- EM portion of the care bundle effectively increased participants' knowledge regarding BSFS and clinical implications based on pre-and post-test scores evaluation
- Zero patient hospitalizations four months post-implementation
- Observed some patients reporting constipation to get laxatives to lose weight

Methods

The seven steps from Iowa Model were followed to guide the creation, implementation, and assessment of this pilot project:

1. Incorporated BSFS into the pilot unit workflow
2. Developed and implemented EM for employees to increase participants' knowledge of BSFS and its clinical implications
3. Coordinated with the IT to develop an EHR alert system to notify licensed staff and MD/NPs of patients' constipation side effects for early management
4. Collected and analyzed surveillance data to assess project impact and outcome

Setting/Participants: Three-unit acute psych facility in SoCal with 48-bed Unit 2 being the pilot setting. 58 level-of-care staff attended EM in-service but only 53 completed pre/post-test and were selected as participants.

Measures: Surveillance of the number of MOM, laxatives, and KUB ordered, pre/post-test eval, surveillance data of hospital admissions w/ constipation

Conclusion & Recommendations

- Patients taking antipsychotics have an increased risk of constipation and impaction
- Using a valid screening tool like the BSFS with the implementation of EM and the PCC alert system is a practical approach and strategy for the early detection and management of AIC
- Further studies are needed on approaches to screening and management of AIC
- BSFS should continue to be used for constipation screening
- Facility-wide implementation recommended, hardwired into nursing policy and procedures
- Future projects should consider patients using laxatives for weight loss